

In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices

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Executive summary

The deliverable reports all relevant information regarding the development of a simplified constitutive model to describe the material behaviour of the vessel wall, which will be used in combination with the virtual device models for preliminary analyses requiring a reduced computational effort. For this purpose, the constitutive framework of the neo-Hookean and the Fung-Demiray model is described, and subsequently the implementation process in the commercial finite element software ANSYS Mechanical APDL and LS-DYNA is detailed. Lastly, two elementary numerical examples are provided.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
TAVI	Transcatheter aortic valve implantation
PAPS	Pulmonary artery pressure sensor

Introduction

SIMCor aims to provide manufacturers of cardiovascular implants with a platform for comprehensive in-silico testing and validation of new devices. In particular, simulation of device effects on two representative areas, *transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI)* and *pulmonary artery pressure sensors (PAPS)*, is addressed. In order to accurately simulate the implantation of a device, the physical properties of its components, including material, structural, geometric and mechanical features, have to be modelled. In addition, the interaction with the tissue requires an accurate characterisation of mechanical properties and microstructure of the vessel wall, together with the development and validation of an appropriate constitutive model.

The scope of this document is to report all the relevant information regarding the development of a simplified constitutive model to describe the material behaviour of the vessel wall, which will be used in combination with the virtual device models for preliminary analyses requiring a reduced computational effort. For this purpose, the mechanical behaviour of the vessel wall is described briefly in *Section Arterial wall*; the simplified constitutive model is presented in *Section Constitutive vessel model*; finally, details of the implementation process in the commercial finite element software ANSYS Mechanical APDL and LS-DYNA, including two elementary examples, are provided in *Section Implementation*.

Arterial wall

Arteries can be classified into two main types: elastic and muscular. Elastic arteries are located close to the heart (e.g., the aorta or the pulmonary artery) while muscular arteries are found towards the periphery (e.g., radial or femoral arteries) [6]. In this research, we will focus on elastic arterial walls, typically consisting of a three-layered arrangement: the inner intimal layer, the medial layer, and the outermost adventitial layer. A visual representation of the healthy arterial wall, showing the three distinct layers, is provided in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the major components of a healthy elastic artery composed of three layers - the Intima (I), the Media (M) and the Adventitia (A) - as shown in [4].

The *intima* is the innermost layer of the arterial wall, and is composed of a single layer of endothelial cells and a subendothelium. The subendothelial layer consists of collagen fibres, arranged non-uniformly through the thickness of the layer. Furthermore, different families of collagen fibres show large deviations of individual fibres from the mean orientations [4]. The healthy, young intima is very thin and does not contribute to the mechanical properties of the arterial wall. However, with age or disease (e.g., arteriosclerosis), the subendothelial layer thickens and stiffens. This, in turn, may result in the intima becoming significant in the contribution to the mechanical response of the arterial wall [6].

The *media* is the middle layer of the arterial wall and consists of an interconnected network of smooth muscle cells, elastin, and collagen fibres. This network creates a continuous fibrous helix, which is almost circumferentially oriented. As a result, the media is able to resist high loads in the circumferential direction, making it the most significant layer in a healthy artery from a mechanical perspective [6, 4].

The *adventitia* is the fibre-reinforced outer layer of the arterial wall, consisting of collagen fibres, fibroblasts, fibrocytes, and histological ground substance [6]. The collagen in the adventitia appears in two fibre families which are both helically arranged, and individual fibres are largely dispersed around the mean orientation of the family [4]. Due to the presence of a relevant soft ground matrix, the adventitial layer behaves much less stiffer than the medial layer. However, when exposed to high pressures the collagen fibril bundles contribute significantly to the strength and stability of the arterial wall. Eventually, collagen fibres at their full length change the adventitia into a stiff tube which prevents the artery from over-stretching and rupturing [6].

Constitutive vessel model

Following the description of the structure of healthy arterial walls, a constitutive model is introduced in this section to describe the passive nonlinear elastic behaviour of arteries. The model adopts the simplifying assumption of isotropic material behaviour and implements two different strain-energy functions, which are typically adopted in the literature for soft polymers and tissues. This constitutive framework can be employed for the whole vessel or applied to each layer, in the case layer-specific experimental data is available.

Kinematics

Let Ω_0 be the (undeformed) reference configuration and Ω the (deformed) current configuration of the continuous body of interest. We can describe the transformation of a material point \mathbf{X} from Ω_0 to Ω using the deformation map χ , such that $\mathbf{x} = \chi(\mathbf{X})$. Accordingly, the deformation gradient tensor $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X})$ is defined as $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}) = \partial\chi(\mathbf{X})/\partial\mathbf{X}$ [5]. Arteries, like many others biological tissues, are known to behave as almost incompressible materials, for which we introduce the well-known constraint on the determinant of the deformation gradient $J = \det(\mathbf{F}) \equiv 1$. However, for computational purposes, it might be beneficial to introduce a multiplicative split of the deformation gradient into volumetric and deviatoric parts. Accordingly, the dilational part of the deformation gradient appears as $J^{1/3}\mathbf{I}$, leaving a purely distortional part $\bar{\mathbf{F}} = J^{-1/3}\mathbf{F}$, with \mathbf{I} the second-order unit tensor. The symmetric right and left Cauchy-Green tensors, which represent the deformation measures in the reference and current configurations respectively, are defined as follows

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{F}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{C}} = J^{-2/3}\mathbf{C}; \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{F}^T, \quad \bar{\mathbf{b}} = J^{-2/3}\mathbf{b}. \quad (2)$$

Finally, we introduce the strain invariants which characterise an isotropic hyperelastic model

$$I_1 = \mathbf{C} : \mathbf{I} = \mathbf{b} : \mathbf{I}, \quad \bar{I}_1 = J^{-2/3}I_1; \quad (3)$$

$$I_2 = J^2\mathbf{C}^{-1} : \mathbf{I} = J^2\mathbf{b}^{-1} : \mathbf{I}, \quad \bar{I}_2 = J^{-4/3}I_2. \quad (4)$$

Strain-energy function

With the assumption of isotropic material behaviour, a strain-energy function can be formulated in terms of the invariants of the Cauchy-Green strain tensors as

$$\Psi = \Psi(I_1, I_2) - p(J - 1), \quad (5)$$

where p serves an indeterminate Lagrange multiplier to enforce the material incompressibility. However, when the multiplicative split of the deformation is adopted, the strain-energy function presents the following additive form

$$\Psi = \Psi_{\text{iso}}(\bar{I}_1, \bar{I}_2) + U(J), \quad (6)$$

where:

- $\Psi_{\text{iso}}(\bar{I}_1, \bar{I}_2)$ is the isochoric part associated with volume-preserving deformations. In this model, two different functions are selected, both neglecting the second strain invariant:

- a linear function of the first strain invariant, known as neo-Hookean strain-energy, which is usually suitable to describe the large strain response of rubber-like materials

$$\Psi_{\text{iso}}^{\text{NH}}(\bar{I}_1) = \frac{\mu}{2}(\bar{I}_1 - 3), \quad (7)$$

where μ the shear modulus of the material.

- An exponential function of the first strain invariant, proposed by Fung and Demiray [3], which is usually suitable to describe the large strain response of soft biological tissues

$$\Psi_{\text{iso}}^{\text{FD}}(\bar{I}_1) = \frac{\mu}{2b} \{ \exp[b(\bar{I}_1 - 3)] - 1 \}, \quad (8)$$

where the additional dimensionless parameter b accounts for the strain-stiffening of the material.

- $U(J)$ is the term associated with volume-changing deformations, usually provided by a convex function of the determinant J . In this model, the following form is chosen

$$U(J) = \frac{K}{2}(J - 1)^2, \quad (9)$$

with K the material bulk modulus.

Stress tensor

A standard procedure leads to the fundamental constitutive equation of isotropic nonlinear elasticity directly expressed in terms of the left Cauchy-Green strain tensor, such that the Cauchy stress tensor in an incompressible material is [5]

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = 2\mathbf{b} \cdot \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{b}} - p\mathbf{I}. \quad (10)$$

Following the additive decomposition of the strain-energy function presented in (6), the Cauchy stress tensor for the modified nearly-incompressible formulation is consequently defined by

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{iso}} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{vol}}, \quad (11)$$

where:

- $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{iso}}$ is the isochoric stress tensor defined as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{iso}} = \mathbb{p} : (2\bar{\mathbf{b}} \cdot \frac{\partial \Psi_{\text{iso}}}{\partial \bar{\mathbf{b}}}) = \mathbb{p} : \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}, \quad (12)$$

where we have introduced the projection tensor $\mathbb{p} = \mathbb{I} - \frac{1}{3}\mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{I}$, with \mathbb{I} the fourth-order identity tensor. The fictitious stress tensor $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ can be written as

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = J^{-1}\psi_1\bar{\mathbf{b}}, \quad (13)$$

with stress coefficient $\psi_1 = 2\partial\bar{\Psi}_{\text{iso}}(\bar{I}_1)/\partial\bar{I}_1$ depending on the choice of the strain-energy function. For the forms introduced in (7)-(8), the expressions are summarised in *Table 1*.

- $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{vol}}$ is the volumetric stress tensor defined as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{vol}} = p\mathbf{I}, \quad (14)$$

with the volumetric stress coefficient $p = dU/dJ$. For the strain-energy introduced in (9), the expression is provided in *Table 1*.

Elasticity tensor

The implementation of a nonlinear material model in an implicit finite element code is based on the linearisation of constitutive equations and requires the definition of an elasticity tensor. Following the modified nearly-incompressible formulation, we have an additive representation of the spatial elasticity tensor as reported below

$$\mathbb{C} = \mathbb{C}_{\text{iso}} + \mathbb{C}_{\text{vol}}, \quad (15)$$

where:

- \mathbb{C}_{iso} is the isochoric elasticity tensor defined as [5]

$$\mathbb{C}_{\text{iso}} = \mathbb{p} : \bar{\mathbb{c}} : \mathbb{p} + \frac{2}{3} \text{tr}(\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}) \mathbb{p} - \frac{2}{3} (\mathbf{I} \otimes \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{iso}} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{iso}} \otimes \mathbf{I}), \quad (16)$$

and the fictitious elasticity tensor $\bar{\mathbb{c}}$ can be written as

$$\bar{\mathbb{c}} = J^{-1} \psi_{11} (\bar{\mathbf{b}} \otimes \bar{\mathbf{b}}), \quad (17)$$

with the elasticity coefficient $\psi_{11} = 4 \partial^2 \bar{\Psi}_{\text{iso}} / \partial \bar{I}_1 \partial \bar{I}_1$ depending on the choice of the strain-energy function. For the forms introduced in (7)-(8), the expressions are summarised in *Table 1*.

- \mathbb{C}_{vol} is the volumetric elasticity tensor defined as

$$\mathbb{C}_{\text{vol}} = \tilde{p} \mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{I} - 2p \mathbb{I}, \quad (18)$$

with the volumetric elasticity coefficient $\tilde{p} = p + J dp/dJ$. For the strain-energy introduced in (9), the expression is provided in *Table 1*.

Variable	Neo-Hookean	Fung-Demiray
Isochoric strain-energy function	$\Psi_{\text{iso}}^{\text{NH}}(\bar{I}_1) = \frac{\mu}{2}(\bar{I}_1 - 3)$	$\Psi_{\text{iso}}^{\text{FD}}(\bar{I}_1) = \frac{\mu}{2b} \{ \exp[b(\bar{I}_1 - 3)] - 1 \}$
Isochoric stress coefficient, see (13)	$\psi_1^{\text{NH}} = \mu$	$\psi_1^{\text{FD}} = \frac{\mu}{2} \exp[b(\bar{I}_1 - 3)]$
Isochoric elasticity coefficient, see (17)	$\psi_{11}^{\text{NH}} = 0$	$\psi_{11}^{\text{FD}} = \frac{\mu b}{2} \exp[b(\bar{I}_1 - 3)]$
Volumetric strain-energy function	$U(J) = \frac{K}{2}(J - 1)^2$	
Volumetric stress coefficient, see (14)	$p = K(J - 1)$	
Volumetric elasticity coefficient, see (18)	$\tilde{p} = K(J - 1) + JK$	

Table 1: Implementation of isotropic constitutive equations with the modified nearly-incompressible formulation.

Implementation

The constitutive model described above is implemented into the commercial finite element software ANSYS Mechanical APDL and LS-DYNA. This section provides details about the definition of the required material parameters and illustrates the model performance with two elementary benchmark cases of uniaxial and equibiaxial extension.

ANSYS Mechanical APDL

Implementation of the constitutive model

ANSYS Mechanical APDL material library includes several hyperelastic constitutive models and provides options for implementing incompressible and nearly-incompressible formulations. However, the software does not provide an in-built material definition of the Fung-Demiray strain-energy shown in (8). Therefore, a user material must be implemented through the subroutine `UserMat`. The `UserMat` is a user-programmable feature for developing a generic isothermal constitutive model through a user-defined FORTRAN code. With respect to hyperelastic material models, it is convenient to formulate the constitutive equations in the total form, which directly employs the deformation gradient passed in to the user-subroutine. The subroutine is then called at each integration point of the elements during the solution phase.

The user material is defined following the constitutive equations presented in *Section Constitutive vessel model*. Specifically, the nearly-incompressible formulation shown in (6) is implemented, with the volumetric strain-energy expressed by

$$U(J) = \frac{1}{d}(J - 1)^2, \quad (19)$$

where $d = 2/K$ is the material incompressibility parameter. Notice that by setting $d = 0$ the material is fully incompressible. Although the neo-Hookean model is available as in-built material, the same user material can also be employed. Indeed, by taking $b \rightarrow 0$ in (8), one obtains $\exp[b(\bar{I}_1 - 3)] \approx b(\bar{I}_1 - 3) + 1$, such that (8) reduces to the neo-Hookean strain-energy (7) [7].

UserMat implementation

The constitutive model is implemented in a FORTRAN code, which is made available to the consortium members as supplementary material ([google.drive](https://drive.google.com)).

The following subroutines are called from the main ANSYS Mechanical APDL subroutine `UserMat`:

- `usermat3D`: subroutine providing the stress in the current configuration (symmetric Cauchy stress tensor `stress`), the Eulerian elasticity tensor (material Jacobian in terms of the Jaumann rate of the Kirchhoff stress `dsdeP1`) and the elastic strain energy `sedE1`. Suitable for 3D, axisymmetric and plane strain elements;
- `estressI1I2`: subroutine computing the isochoric (fictitious) part of the Cauchy stress tensor;
- `etensI1I2`: subroutine computing the isochoric (fictitious) part of the spatial elasticity tensor;
- `devetens`: subroutine computing the deviatoric part of the spatial elasticity tensor.

In addition, the following user-defined utility subroutines are called throughout the code:

- `identity`: subroutine providing the identity tensor and its dyadics;
- `voigt2`: subroutine transforming a symmetric second-order tensor in matrix form into Voigt's notation;
- `bdet`: subroutine computing the determinant of a (3x3) matrix;
- `dyad6`: subroutine computing the dyadic product of two symmetric second-order tensors in Voigt's notation;
- `sym4tens66`: subroutine computing the symmetrised square dyadic product of two symmetric second-order tensors in Voigt's notation;
- `contract66`: subroutine computing the double contraction of two fourth-order tensors with major symmetries in Voigt's notation;
- `poldecomp`: subroutine computing the right polar decomposition of the deformation gradient.

According to the software documentation [1], ANSYS Mechanical APDL adopts a corotational formulation, meaning that all tensor quantities should be expressed with respect to an orthogonal basis that follows the rigid rotation at the material point \mathbf{R} , being $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{U}$ the right polar decomposition of the deformation gradient [5], with \mathbf{U} the symmetric right stretch tensor. For this reason, in order to avoid to rotate back the stress and elasticity tensors from the spatial to the corotational basis, the constitutive equations summarised in *Section Constitutive vessel model* are directly formulated in terms of the stretch tensor \mathbf{U} . Accordingly, the left Cauchy-Green tensor is expressed as $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{F}^T = \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{U} \cdot \mathbf{U} \cdot \mathbf{R}^T = \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{U}^2 \cdot \mathbf{R}^T$, such that for instance the fictitious Cauchy stress in (13) is written as

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \mathbf{R} \cdot (J^{-1} \psi_1 \bar{\mathbf{U}}^2) \cdot \mathbf{R}^T, \quad (20)$$

where the term in parenthesis is precisely the corotational stress, and $\bar{\mathbf{U}} = J^{-1/3} \mathbf{U}$.

Finally, we recall that tensors should be stored in matrix format using Voigt's notation; to give an example, the second-order Cauchy stress tensor is represented as

$$[\boldsymbol{\sigma}] = [\sigma_{11} \ \sigma_{22} \ \sigma_{33} \ \sigma_{12} \ \sigma_{23} \ \sigma_{13}]^T. \quad (21)$$

Required input

Material models in ANSYS Mechanical APDL are specified through the command **TB**, followed by the command **TBDATA** to pass in the material parameters. A summary of the parameters and keywords required for the user material is reported in *Table 2*.

Software quality assurance

The user-material subroutine here developed is provided as FORTRAN source code (FORTRAN 90 or later) and needs to be compiled by using a proper FORTRAN compiler. All the results provided as benchmark problems were obtained by running ANSYS Mechanical APDL 2021 R1 and Intel Fortran Compiler 2022.0.2, included in the Intel oneAPI Base and Intel oneAPI HPC Toolkits, combined with Microsoft Visual Studio 2019. The user-material subroutine has been linked into a Dynamic-link (DLL) Library, as specified in the software documentation [1]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, there are no known compiler-related issues that could affect the application of the implemented user-defined subroutine.

Definition	Keyword	Value
TB command		
Material model type	Lab	USER
Data table specification	TBOPT ¹	-
Number of data points	NPTS	3
TBDATA command		
Material incompressibility parameter d	C1	t.b.d.
Shear modulus μ	C2	t.b.d.
Material strain-stiffening parameter b ²	C3	t.b.d.

Table 2: Summary of material parameters and keywords required for the implementation of the proposed constitutive model with the `UserMat` subroutine in ANSYS Mechanical APDL.

¹ If not specified, the default value of TBOPT is NONLINEAR. However, if the material behaviour is considered fully incompressible, a mixed element formulation should be selected by setting TBOPT=MXUP.

² The neo-Hookean strain-energy function is implemented by taking $b \rightarrow 0$.

Benchmark problems

To illustrate the constitutive behaviour described by the model, we have selected two boundary value problems, which can be solved explicitly in the case of perfect incompressibility by considering the plane stress assumption. Let us introduce here the spectral decomposition of the deformation gradient [5]

$$\mathbf{F} = \sum_{a=1}^3 \lambda_a \mathbf{e}_a \otimes \mathbf{E}_a, \quad (22)$$

where the eigenvalues λ_a are principal stretches and the eigenvectors $\mathbf{e}_a, \mathbf{E}_a$ represent the principal spatial and referential basis vectors, respectively.

The strain-energy function (5) combined with expression (8) can be reformulated in terms of the principal stretches as follows

$$\hat{\Psi}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3) = \frac{\mu}{2b} \{ \exp[b(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_3^2 - 3)] - 1 \} - p(\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 - 1). \quad (23)$$

The principal Cauchy stress is obtained as [5]

$$\sigma_a = \lambda_a \frac{\partial \hat{\Psi}}{\partial \lambda_a} - p, \quad \text{with} \quad \frac{\partial \hat{\Psi}}{\partial \lambda_a} = \mu \lambda_a \exp[b(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_3^2 - 3)], \quad (24)$$

where p is a Lagrange multiplier determined by imposing the plane stress condition $\sigma_3 = 0$.

The numerical solution is obtained using ANSYS Mechanical APDL static analysis, on a single 8-node element (SOLID185) with full integration and mixed formulation for material incompressibility. The parameters used in the benchmark problems are listed in *Table 3*. Note that these are canonical values for soft materials and therefore are not calibrated to the real tissue.

Neo-Hookean		
Material parameter	Value	Unit
Incompressibility parameter d	0.0	1/kPa
Shear modulus μ	10.0	kPa
Strain-stiffening parameter b	1e-6	-
Fung-Demiray		
Incompressibility parameter d	0.0	1/kPa
Shear modulus μ	10.0	kPa
Strain-stiffening parameter b	5.0	-

Table 3: Summary of material parameters employed in the numerical solution of the benchmark problems for neo-Hookean and Fung-Demiray strain-energy functions.

Benchmark I: Uniaxial Extension

A uniaxial deformation can be defined in terms of principal stretches as follows

$$x_1 = \lambda X_1, \quad x_2 = \lambda^{-1/2} X_2, \quad x_3 = \lambda^{-1/2} X_3, \quad (25)$$

where we have assumed that the principal direction \mathbf{E}_1 is aligned with the axis of an experimental uniaxial protocol. The corresponding deformation gradient is

$$\mathbf{F} = \lambda \mathbf{e}_1 \otimes \mathbf{E}_1 + \lambda^{-1/2} \mathbf{e}_2 \otimes \mathbf{E}_2 + \lambda^{-1/2} \mathbf{e}_3 \otimes \mathbf{E}_3. \quad (26)$$

The principal Cauchy stress components, from (24), are

$$\sigma_1 = \mu(\lambda^2 - \lambda^{-1}) \exp[b(\lambda^2 + 2\lambda^{-1} - 3)], \quad \sigma_2 = \sigma_3 = 0. \quad (27)$$

A comparison between analytical solution (27) and numerical results is illustrated in *Figures 2-3*.

Benchmark II: Equibiaxial Extension

An equibiaxial deformation can be defined in terms of principal stretches as follows

$$x_1 = \lambda X_1, \quad x_2 = \lambda X_2, \quad x_3 = \lambda^{-2} X_3, \quad (28)$$

where we have assumed that the principal directions $\mathbf{E}_1, \mathbf{E}_2$ are aligned with the axes of an experimental biaxial protocol. The corresponding deformation gradient is

$$\mathbf{F} = \lambda \mathbf{e}_1 \otimes \mathbf{E}_1 + \lambda \mathbf{e}_2 \otimes \mathbf{E}_2 + \lambda^{-2} \mathbf{e}_3 \otimes \mathbf{E}_3. \quad (29)$$

The principal Cauchy stress components, from (24), are

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \mu(\lambda^2 - \lambda^{-4}) \exp[b(2\lambda^2 + \lambda^{-4} - 3)], \quad \sigma_3 = 0. \quad (30)$$

A comparison between analytical solution (30) and numerical results is illustrated in *Figures 4-5*.

Figure 2: Uniaxial extension, neo-Hookean material model. Comparison between analytical and numerical results obtained from ANSYS Mechanical APDL.

Figure 3: Uniaxial extension, Fung-Demiray material model. Comparison between analytical and numerical results obtained from ANSYS Mechanical APDL.

Figure 4: Equibiaxial extension, neo-Hookean material model. Comparison between analytical and numerical results obtained from ANSYS Mechanical APDL.

Figure 5: Equibiaxial extension, Fung-Demiray material model. Comparison between analytical and numerical results obtained from ANSYS Mechanical APDL.

Basics (Card 1)					
Definition			Keyword		Value
Material identification			MID		1
Mass density ¹			ρ		1.0
Material axes option			AOPT		0.0
Isotropic part (Card 2)			Isotropic part (Card 2.1c)		
Definition	Keyword	Value	Definition	Keyword	Value
Module title	TITLE	ISO	Holzappel-Ogden modulus	k_1	t.b.d.
Type of isotropic model ²	ITYPE	-3	Holzappel-Ogden constant	k_2	t.b.d.
Volumetric coefficient	β	0.0			
Poisson's ratio	ν	t.b.d.			

Table 4: Summary of material parameters and keywords for LS-DYNA material model *MAT_295. The combination presented here implements a nearly-incompressible, isotropic material behaviour with an isochoric exponential strain-energy function.

¹ Mass density is not relevant for the implicit algorithm.

² ITYPE=-3 implements the isochoric exponential strain-energy function as in (31).

LS-DYNA

Implementation of the constitutive model

LS-DYNA offers a vast material library with several constitutive models suitable for isotropic hyperelastic response. With specific reference to soft biological tissues, the material identified by the code *MAT_295 provides a modular framework for incompressible or nearly-incompressible, isotropic and anisotropic hyperelastic constitutive models [2]. Different options are available, which are specified by so-called material cards. In this section, this material will be employed to implement the proposed constitutive model, considering both the neo-Hookean and Fung-Demiray strain-energy functions, with a nearly-incompressible behaviour. Since both strain-energy functions are isotropic, the anisotropic material card is disabled; furthermore, the definition of a local material orientation is not relevant.

The general form of the strain-energy function implemented in *MAT_295 is analogous to the one described in *Section Constitutive vessel model*; for better clarity, we keep here the original notation employed in the software user manual [2]. Adopting the modified nearly-incompressible formulation shown in (6), the isochoric isotropic part is expressed by

$$\Psi_{\text{iso}}(\bar{I}_1) = \frac{k_1}{2k_2} \{ \exp[k_2(\bar{I}_1 - 3)] - 1 \}, \quad (31)$$

where $k_1 \equiv \mu$ is the material shear modulus and $k_2 \equiv b$ is the dimensionless parameter accounting for strain-stiffening. At this point, we notice that this strain-energy function directly implements the exponential Fung-Demiray model (8). Furthermore, by taking $k_2 \equiv b \rightarrow 0$, we obtain $\exp[k_2(\bar{I}_1 - 3)] \approx k_2(\bar{I}_1 - 3) + 1$, such that (31) reduces to the neo-Hookean strain-energy (7) [7]. A summary of the material parameters and keywords required is reported in *Table 4*.

Benchmark problems

The solution of the benchmark problems in LS-DYNA and its comparison with the analytical results is not reported here since the material model is in-built in the software. The reader is instead referred to *Deliverable 9.1 Constitutive vessel model (TUG, M18)* dedicated to the implementation and verification of the enhanced constitutive model.

Discussion

The constitutive frameworks of the neo-Hookean model and the Fung-Demiray model were successfully implemented in the commercial finite element software ANSYS Mechanical APDL and LS-DYNA. Since both models are implemented in the in-built model *MAT_295 in LS-DYNA, it was not necessary to perform a verification study in this case. Thus, only the keywords are provided in this deliverable. On the contrary, we implemented the neo-Hookean model and the Fung-Demiray model into the UserMat subroutine of ANSYS Mechanical APDL. Verification activities were therefore required. The comparison between an analytical solution of an equibiaxial extension test and a uniaxial extension test showed that the results of the numerical solution (ANSYS Mechanical APDL) is in good agreement with the analytical solution. Finally, it should be noticed that both models are isotropic and therefore only provide an approximation to the mechanical behaviour of the vessel, which is anisotropic due to the arrangement of the collagen fibres. In general, the neo-Hookean strain-energy can describe the behaviour of the tissue at low stretches while the exponential Fung-Demiray model can also capture the characteristic strain-stiffening behaviour at higher stretches.

In the next step, the material parameters of this model are determined (*Deliverable 8.4 Validated constitutive models of the vessel wall (TUG, M20)*) and the enhanced constitutive model (*Deliverable 9.1 Constitutive vessel model (TUG, M18)*) is developed on the basis of this constitutive framework.

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